

Access to and Engagement with Mathematics Across the Transition from Primary to Post-Primary School: Teacher Knowledge and Perceptions

Lorraine Harbison¹, Ian Cantley², Mark Prendergast³, Niamh O'Meara⁴ and Clare O'Hara⁵

¹Dublin City University, ² Queen's University Belfast, ³ University College Cork, ⁴ University of Limerick and ⁵Central Statistics Office

Research surrounding the transition has frequently cited the quality of students' interaction with teachers as having a significant association with engagement in mathematics. Thus in this cross-border study we employed a questionnaire with the aim of capturing teachers' knowledge and perceptions that underpin their instructional practices and ultimately impact on student achievement. A representative sample of 428 primary and 248 post-primary mathematics teachers from across both jurisdictions responded. The findings show that most primary teachers consider mathematics easier than other subjects to teach with only around 10% of post-primary teachers perceiving this to be the case. With the exception of post-primary teachers in Northern Ireland, perceived levels of content knowledge of the preceding/ensuing stage are low. All teachers reported a high sense of confidence in relation to teaching all strands across the mathematics curriculum and answering students' questions in class. Primary teachers were more likely to consider students well prepared in all strands of the curriculum upon exiting primary school than post-primary teachers. This disagreement was more pronounced when considering Algebra than any other strand. In this paper, we consider how these findings shape instructional practice and thus influence students access to and engagement with mathematics.

Introduction

Teachers play a central role in students' education and in their transition experience with positive interactions being associated with a greater interest in, and reduced difficulty with, mathematics (Smyth, 2017). The quality of these interactions are mediated by a teacher's impressions of mathematics and their own self-assurance in their pedagogical competency while interacting within particular environmental contexts (Cantley et al., 2021).

Following an evaluation of primary to post-primary transition arrangements for mathematics in NI, the Education and Training Inspectorate (2010) reported that teachers at either side of the boundary crossing had insufficient awareness of the curriculum and pedagogy employed in the other phase. To address this perceived knowledge deficit, a continuing professional development (CPD) project for teachers at either side of the transition, which specifically targeted mathematics (and also literacy) provision, was funded by the Department of Education in NI and commenced in January 2015. The CPD project sought to furnish teachers of mathematics in both phases with high-quality professional learning experiences, delivered via face-to-face training and supported by a virtual learning environment hosting a range of relevant resources, to promote the development of cross-phase curricular and pedagogical knowledge and skills. Between January 2015 and June 2016, a two-day training programme was offered to post-primary mathematics teachers, and two half-

day training sessions were offered to primary school teachers. Funding was also provided to release primary and post-primary teachers of mathematics from normal teaching duties for two days to facilitate cross-phase collaboration (involving, for example, joint planning, joint staff development, and joint classroom observation). However, this was a once-off initiative and there was no similar transition-related CPD provision in RoI when the research was undertaken.

Thus, in this research, we investigated the four key elements that relate to *Teacher Knowledge and Perceptions* as detailed by Campbell et al. (2014). Specifically, we sought to ascertain the knowledge and perceptions of primary and post-primary teachers who teach in the year prior or subsequent to the transition in both the Republic of Ireland (RoI) and Northern Ireland (NI). Therefore, the questions that informed our study were:

1. What are teachers' self-perceptions of their knowledge of mathematical content in the preceding or ensuing stage?
2. How do they rate their own confidence in teaching mathematics?
3. What are their beliefs regarding mathematics teaching and learning?
4. Do teachers consider that they are familiar with students' dispositions and previous or forthcoming mathematical experiences?

These elements are particularly important as such *Knowledge and Perceptions* shape teachers' *Instructional Practice* and thus have an impact on *Student Achievement* (Campbell et al., 2014).

Methods

A teacher research advisory group was established to guide the development of two data collection instruments, a 6th Class/Year 7 Primary Teacher Questionnaire and a 1st Year/Year 8 Post-Primary Mathematics Teacher Questionnaire, and inform subsequent distribution to research participants. The sampling frame consisted of 3,300 primary and 723 post-primary schools in RoI as well as 827 primary and 202 post-primary schools in NI. On the basis of feedback from the teacher research advisory group, a random sample of 700 (RoI) and 450 (NI) primary schools as well as 400 (RoI) and 300 (NI) post-primary schools were selected. To allow a comparison to be drawn, the questionnaires employed across both jurisdictions and levels differed only with regards to specific terminology utilised in these contexts. Questions were designed to mirror the four key elements of *Teacher Knowledge and Perceptions* namely: knowledge of mathematical content in the preceding or ensuing stage; confidence in teaching mathematics; beliefs regarding mathematics teaching and learning; and awareness of students' prior or subsequent mathematical experiences and dispositions (Campbell et al., 2014, p. 423).

Results and Analysis

Participants

In total, 428 primary teachers returned completed questionnaires, which included 298 from RoI and 130 from NI, representing response rates of 42.6% and 28.9% respectively. In

addition, 248 post-primary teachers responded to the questionnaire, including 173 from RoI and 75 from NI, which represented response rates of 43.3% and 25% respectively.

Mathematical Content Knowledge

Teachers were asked to indicate their perceptions of familiarity with the mathematical curriculum content and teaching methodologies in the proceeding/ensuing phase, a term commonly known as horizon content knowledge. Familiarity with such horizon knowledge is deemed to have an impact on teachers' decisions regarding "appropriate pedagogical approaches to use when teaching particular topics in the curriculum, so as to align with both prior and future learning" (Cantley et al., 2021, p. 43). Primary teachers in RoI indicated slightly higher levels of knowledge of post-primary curricula than their NI counterparts. However, despite the more positive views expressed by RoI teachers, the difference in perceived mathematical content knowledge between RoI and NI primary teachers was not statistically significant. Primary teachers in both jurisdictions revealed similar levels of familiarity with the recommended teaching methods for post-primary mathematics. On the other hand, post-primary teachers in NI indicated statistically significant higher levels of familiarity with both the curriculum ($p < .001$) and recommended teaching methods ($p < .001$) for final year primary mathematics than their counterparts in RoI (Table 1).

Table 1

Primary and Post-Primary Teachers' Perceptions of Mathematical Content Knowledge

	Jurisdiction	Highly unfamiliar	Somewhat unfamiliar	Neither familiar nor unfamiliar	Somewhat familiar	Highly familiar
Familiarity with curriculum for first year post-primary mathematics	RoI (n=296)	29.7%	26.4%	6.8%	27.4%	9.8%
	NI (n=130)	31.5%	32.3%	11.5%	22.3%	2.3%
Familiarity with teaching methods for first year post-primary mathematics	RoI (n=294)	45.9%	26.5%	13.6%	9.9%	4.1%
	NI (n=128)	42.2%	28.1%	14.8%	14.1%	0.8%
Familiarity with curriculum for final year primary mathematics	RoI (n=173)	24.3%	28.3%	7.5%	31.8%	8.1%
	NI (n=75)	4.0%	21.3%	1.3%	57.3%	16.0%
Familiarity with teaching methods for final year primary mathematics	RoI (n=173)	43.4%	32.9%	8.1%	12.7%	2.9%
	NI (n=75)	17.3%	33.3%	16.0%	26.7%	6.7%

Pedagogical Content Knowledge for Mathematics

Teachers were asked to rate their confidence in teaching all areas of the mathematics curriculum. Primary teachers reported being most confident in teaching Number (Figure 1). Thus we compared responses from those who perceived they were *Highly Confident* in Number to each of the other strands. In both jurisdictions, primary teachers were statistically not as *Highly Confident* in teaching Algebra as Number ($p < .001$). Furthermore, primary teachers in RoI were statistically not as *Highly Confident* in teaching Shape and space ($p < .001$), and Measures ($p < .05$), as Number, whereas a comparison of Number with Data was nearly significant ($p = .06$).

Figure 1

Primary Teachers Pedagogical Content Knowledge for Mathematics

The majority of post-primary teachers in both jurisdictions perceived that they had high pedagogical knowledge across all strands of the mathematics curriculum (Table 2).

Table 2

Post-Primary Teachers Pedagogical Content Knowledge for Mathematics

Strand	Number	Number	Algebra	Algebra	Functions	Geometry	Geometry	Data	Data
Jurisdiction	NI	RoI	NI	RoI	RoI	NI	RoI	NI	RoI
Highly confident	96%	85.3%	94.6%	90.6%	81.2%	93.3%	77.6%	92%	60.6%
Somewhat confident	1.3%	14.1%	2.7%	7.6%	16.5%	4%	20.6%	5.3%	30%
Other	2.7%	0.6%	2.7%	1.8%	2.3%	2.7%	1.8%	2.7%	9.4%

Beliefs Regarding Mathematics Teaching and Learning

The third element was to examine teachers’ perceptions of mathematics teaching and learning more broadly. Primary teachers (57.5% RoI, 57.8% NI) consider mathematics easier than most subjects to teach with only around 10% of post-primary teachers agreeing (12% RoI, 8.1% NI; chi sq. $p < .001$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2

It is Easier to Teach Mathematics Than Other Subjects

Note. Data labels indicate the percentage of teachers who strongly disagreed.

However, teachers at both levels and in both jurisdictions believed that they are well able to answer students’ questions in class (Table 3).

Table 3

I am generally well able to answer students’ questions about mathematics in class.

	Primary teachers	Post-primary teachers
Strongly or somewhat agree	RoI (96.3%) NI (97%)	RoI (95.3%) NI (98.7%)

Awareness of Students’ Prior Mathematical Experiences and Dispositions

Regarding students’ prior mathematical experiences, teachers were asked if they perceived that students were well prepared in all curriculum areas upon exiting from primary school or entering post-primary. As can be seen from Figure 3, primary teachers perceived that students had strong mathematical experiences from which to build upon in post-primary school. This is in sharp contrast to post-primary teachers’ perceptions. Particular concern was expressed about students’ lack of foundational skills in Algebra. Over 70% of primary teachers in both jurisdictions agreed or strongly agreed that students were well prepared in

Algebra as opposed to just 8.8% and 16.2% of post-primary teachers in RoI and NI respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Comparison of Post-Primary Teachers' Perceptions of Students' Prior Mathematical Experiences with that of Primary Teachers

Perceptions of students' dispositions towards mathematics can further influence the types of pedagogical practices teachers employ. Less than half of primary teachers in RoI (44%) and slightly more than half of primary teachers in NI (51.5%) believe that it is difficult to change students' attitudes towards mathematics. In comparison to their counterparts, 72% of teachers in NI consider that students' dispositions towards mathematics are already firmly established before they start in post-primary school ($p = .006$). Whereas just half of post-primary teachers in RoI perceive that students' dispositions towards mathematics are already firmly established, the majority of teachers (68%) favoured a fresh start approach to teaching students on entry to post-primary school over garnering information about students' mathematical dispositions from the primary school or using assessments to build up a profile of a student's prior learning.

Implications

The findings from this research call for the development of transition-related mathematics professional learning opportunities for teachers. The potential benefits of a cross-phase CPD would address issues of teachers' knowledge and perceptions of mathematics at transition and therefore support students' access to and engagement with mathematics.

References

- Campbell, P.F., Nishio, M., Smith, T.M., Clark, L.M., Conant, D.L., Rust, A.H., DePiper, J.M., Frank, T.J., Griffin, M.J., & Choi, Y. (2014). The relationship between teachers' mathematical content and pedagogical knowledge, teachers' perceptions, and student achievement. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 45(4), 419-459.
- Cantley I., O'Meara, N., Prendergast, M., Harbison, L. & O'Hara, C. (2021). Framework for analysing continuity in students' learning experiences during primary to secondary transition in mathematics. *Irish Educational Studies*, 40(1), 37-49.
- Education and Training Inspectorate. (2010). *Transition in mathematics: Primary to post-primary*. Belfast: Author.
- Smyth, E. (2017). *Growing up in Ireland, Report no.5: Off to a good start? Primary school experiences and the transition to second-level education*. Dublin: Stationery Office.